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AN INQUIRY INTO SOCIAL ASPECTS OF OBJECTS: EVOLUTION OF PRAYER BEADS INTO DIGITAL COUNTERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the study which focused on the use of prayer beads. Prayer beads, which are the objects used for counting prayers, are evolving into digital counters, during the last decade in Turkey. Focusing on this evolution, the current study aims to explain social and cultural aspects of using a product. For this purpose, first a brief theoretical framework on material culture of consumption and everyday life is provided within the specificity of how Islam informs these in Turkish context. A brief history of prayer beads is given based on the field study. The field study is composed of semi-structured interviews with tarika members and regular attendants of a mosque, and observations in these fields which elaborates on the meaning of objects and daily practices, the co-evolution of objects and practices, how social, cultural, and religious values inform the use and appropriation of objects.

(146 words should be utmost 150)

Keywords: Material culture, design research, prayer beads.

INTRODUCTION

The current study presents conclusions, findings and insights based on a master's thesis study (Tonuk, 2011), which was inspired by an ethnographic study conducted within the scope of a graduate course titled as *Seminar on Ethnographic Field Research* which was offered by the Social Anthropology Program at the Middle East Technical University. The field of the ethnographic study was a sacred religious site which consisted of a shrine, a mosque, an

ancient temple and a highly commercialized shopping area, where a variety of consumption goods from conventional products to modern, technological ones demonstrated a developed market of products targeted for religious purposes. The seemingly contradictory combination of 'spirituality' and 'the extent of consumption' in such a religious site was the start of my inquiry. Having been trained as an industrial designer, I felt the urge to inquire into this seemingly 'paradoxical relationship', which was based on a presupposed contradiction between Islam and consumption.. Therefore, my initial question was how and why these products were used.

Design is a profession which is among the most influential agents in shaping of objects in the modern world and creation of material culture and consumption items, so designers are able to determine various aspects of the interaction between subject, object and practice. Hence designers are supposed to have insight into how products will be used physically and utilized in socio-cultural context. (Shove et. al., 2007) Therefore, design research should inquire into material culture of consumption to provide insight for how and why objects are used and appropriated within the modern social context, by taking an interdisciplinary perspective and elaborating on material culture, which inquires into the intricate and mutual relationship between social context, subject and object, provides an analytical tool to understand these aspects of use and user by unwrapping how and why human subjects use and appropriate objects.

By focusing on prayer bead, which is a conventional object used to count prayers, I aim to explore how and why these objects are used and appropriated by

users in the conduct of their daily life, which is organized around religious precepts. This object which has been used for about 5000 years by most religions is evolving into digital counters, in the last decade in Turkish Islamic context. I focused on this evolution of prayer beads to inquire into the use and utilization of objects, by elaborating on the meaning of these objects, in which socio-cultural context these objects and their usage are shaped, why and how there is this much variety of products, what does consuming these objects imply for, how the evolution from prayer beads to digital counters should have influenced the interaction between the user and the object and how prayer practice is organized within daily life.

THEORISING USE OF OBJECTS AND DAILY PRACTICES & THE ISLAMIC CONTEXT IN TURKEY

The in-depth inquiry into the use of objects by subjects reveals the mutual relationship between the two, where the subject constitutes the object and the object constitutes the subject, emphasizing the intricate relationship between socio-cultural context, subject and materiality. (Miller 2005; Bourdieu 2004; Slater, 1997) Therefore this study inquires into material culture of consumption which inquires into the intricate relationship between human subjects and world of objects within the specificity of practices, thus providing an analytical tool for unfolding object use.

However, as Miller (2006) states, consumption, until 1980s was approached with an anti-material prejudice due to the negative association of consuming that lies in the definition of the activity itself. The Latin origin of the word *consumere* means to take wholly/entirely, eat, devour, destroy. (Skeat, 1910, Patridge, 1966, Klein, 1966), therefore consumption is defined as a destructive force. (Babcock, Gove et. al., 1966)

Miller (2006) argues that, besides the negative connotation of the word itself, the anti-materialist perspective of South Asian religions, such as Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism, where satisfying desires by consumption results in the sullyng of the essence of humanity in mere materialism, lies deep

within the negative connotation of consumption. (Miller, 2006)

However, a comparison of Islam with Abrahamic religions, Hindu religions and Far East Religions reveals a difference in the world view on materiality among these religions. Instead of holding a position against materiality and insulting material bonds and regarding this world as illusionary (Demir 1995; Miller 2005), Islam sees the world and the living and non-living things that are created by Allah as a reflection of Him and His grace, thus Islam regards material environment as valuable and respectable. (Demir, 1995)

Moreover, although Islam and consumption are assumed to be contradictory, Islam encourages consumption and commercial activities, in which Muslims can seek profit and benefit from the material world, as long as these are fair. (Demir, 1995) Especially within the context of living Islam in Turkey, which is a secular modern country, it is argued that consumption has always been a primary means by which identity, individuality, and sociality are constructed and expressed. (Navaro-Yashin, 2002; Saktanber, 2002; Sandıkcı and Ger, 2010)

For Miller (2006) and Shove et. al. (2007), the moral stance to consumption regarding it as evil and destructive held a dominant approach on studies of consumption, until 1980s when sociological and anthropological studies revolutionized this view. Milestone works, one of Thorstein Veblen's (1899, *The Theory of Leisure Class*) which is regarded as the pioneer of approaches sets objects as a means of producing, transmitting, and reproducing social meanings. In addition to this two anthropological works towards the end of 1970s contributed to the sociological approach. Two studies one of Bourdieu's (2003), in which goods are seen not only as carriers of meaning related to status but also means of expressing these meanings, and the other of Douglas' (2000) analysing goods in analogy with language and addressing them as a symbolic system. These studies were path breaking for consumption and material culture studies, as consumption was rendered as a regenerative process of meaning production and expression.

As Miller (2006) argues, within sociology material culture inquiring into material specificity provides an analytical insight to consumption. Material specificity, which results from the very materiality of objects, emphasizes specific conditions, specific groups and specific usages of objects. Therefore in this study material culture perspective is adopted to unfold the relationship between subject and object from within the various levels of this relationship to analyse object use.

At this point it might be useful to suggest that an approach which regards objects only as meaning carriers is not adequate on its own to explain the use of these objects. Due to their very physicality by being employed in the accomplishment of certain practices objects shape how things are done and how daily life is organised. Therefore, everyday objects, routinized daily practices and their mutual relationship, i.e., one constituting the other, and co-evolution of objects and practices, i.e., change in one altering the other, are seen worthy of examining for enlightening the relationship between subject and object. (Shove et. al., 2007; Miller, 2010; Dant, 2005).

However, practices are not defined as only doing things. For practice theory, both social order and individuality work through practices, where body, objects and knowledge are seen as a whole which act together in a routinized way for the accomplishment of a practice where practices are a blend of individual and social knowledge that are embedded in the mental scheme of individuals. (Bourdieu, 2004; Reckwitz, 2002) Practices are embodied structures of routinized, habitual, repeated actions, thus understanding practices requires the understanding of the context within which certain practices are formed. (Shove 2007, Dant 2005, Warde 2005)

Bourdieu defines this context, in which various social classes demonstrate dynamic and organic structure, as *habitus*:

“The structures constitutive of a particular type of environment (e.g. the material condition of existence characteristic of a class condition) produce *habitus*, systems of durable, transposable dispositions...”
(Bourdieu, 2004, p107)

By living in the *habitus* and being raised up in that *habitus*, individuals have embedded knowledge on these practices, which is expressed in their routinized behaviour. Hence, practices are seen as ways of orienting and negotiating in the society (Bourdieu, 2003, Warde, 2005, DeCerteau 1984, Foucault, 1980)

For Foucault (1980), functioning of the society is based on power relationships. “Power is what says no”. (Foucault, 1980, p 139) De Certeau (1984), interested in the ways of makings of users, inquires into the logic of practices within power relationships, as well. For De Certeau (1984), power is the strength of the man of influence or imposed order, and he calls these as strategies. Yet, there are also the actions of the weak, who try to operate in the society, which he calls as tactics within the mainstream strategies. De Certeau (1984, xvii) defines tactic as “the ingenious ways in which the weak makes use of the strong, thus lend a political dimension to everyday practices”. He states that most everyday practices are tactical in character.

As Mardin (2006) argues, “Islam has a more direct relation to the content of social structure than many other religions”. For Islam, the ritual and lifestyle dimensions are said to be emphasized (Repstad, 2006). For Kurtz (1995), “religion is not a part of the structure of Islamic society... it is his or her life.” Religious tradition is ‘diffused’ throughout a believer’s life, where “many daily activities such as eating become acts of faith that reflect a worldview and/ or link the individual in a special way with the religious community.” (Kurtz, 1995) For Kurtz (1995), “religious life is coterminous with everyday life”, as he states, religious rituals “help to frame daily life by regulating such matters as hygiene, diet and sex...” and he emphasizes the five pillars of Islam, stating *salat*¹, which frames the entire day of Muslims, is a daily practice.

So Islamic religion, by organizing all aspects of the daily life of a believer and shaping its whole practice, can be seen as the daily life itself of a believer. Based on the above definitions on religion, emphasizing the routine and embedded structure of religious doctrine in daily life of Muslims, it can be

¹ Salat is one of the five pillars of Islam, in which Muslims are required to perform a ritual prayer five times a day

argued that Islam is a daily practice. (Tönük, 2010) In Turkey which is a modern secular country daily practices of these devoted Muslim group will be analyzed as tactics that devoted Muslims use to negotiate and express themselves in the general order of a modern secular society.

Moreover, Warde (2005) who places practices at the core of social structure as well, renders 'daily practices' as the fundamental drive for social life. He suggests that all consumption is result of practices. For Warde (2005), consumption, rather than being a daily practice, is a moment in all practices, and being a 'competent practitioner' requires use of or owning appropriate tools (Warde, 2005). Accordingly, objects are rendered as the primary agent of practices. Hence prayer beads which are used in worshipping practices will be seen as tools to accomplish practices and specificity of prayer practice will be inquired into by field study.

SPECIFICITY OF PRAYER BEADS: HISTORY OF PRAYER BEADS IN TURKEY

Prayer beads are the row of beads on a string that are used to count or accompany prayers. People pray to unite with the God (Kelly, 2004), to ask for remedy (Kelly 2004), or to achieve a spiritual illumination (Iqbal, 1930). Neither the reason(s) why people started to count their prayers nor an exact history of prayer beads are known.

First, about 5000 years ago Hindus were known to use pebbles in a pouch to count their prayers. (Sarıcı, 2008) Prayer beads, similar to their contemporary form of beads lined up on a string, date back to before 7th century A.D. (Yıldırım, 1971) In every religion and culture there are different numbers of prayers devoted to God each day. Accordingly, the number of beads on a prayer bead varies.

For Islam, there are two sorts of worshipping practices in which prayers are counted or accompanied by prayer beads: Salat and *Dhikr*². As stated in the Qur'an these are incumbent on Muslims and they are important for sins to be forgiven. (*Qur'an* trans by Haleem, 2005; Yıldırım, 1971).

These are performed in various numbers depending on the sect, so different prayer beads or counters are used to accompany these practices. The following part on the recent history of prayer beads is structured based on the data gathered through the field study, and visuals are the photos of the products that are gathered and documented during the field study.

After each salat, it was advised by the Prophet Muhammad to recite 33 times Subhanallah (Glory be to Allah), 33 times Alhamdulillah (Praise be to Allah) and 33 times Allahuakhbar (Allah is great). (Yıldırım, 1971) devoted Muslims in Turkey use '*salat tasbih*'³ which is used to count 33 times 3 prayers after each salat. Salat tasbih consists of 99 beads, that has an indicator bead after every 33 to mark the changing prayer. (Figure1) Some *tarikas*⁴ within Islam, pray the first prayer 34 times so their tasbihs are arranged accordingly, having an indicator bead after 34 beads, and in this case their tasbih consists of 100 beads. (Sarıcı, 2008)

Figure1. Salat tasbih with 99 beads that has an indicator bead after each 33 beads.

Dhikr, which is a kind of prayer, is a remembrance of Allah (Kassam, 2006). Dhikr of Allah, either by reciting one of His qualities or His name only, or His Messenger, is a devotional act that reinforces one's bonds with Allah, is a communication with Allah, is appraisal to Him, as well as emphasis of His glory (Kassam, 2006; Yıldırım, 1971)

To count the extreme numbers that the prayers are recited, Muslims use tasbihs with 100, 500 or 1000 beads or digital counters. (Figure2)

² Dhikr is allusion in the context of Islam

³ Tasbih means prayer bead in the context of Islam

⁴ Tariqa means sect in the context of Islam

Figure2. Tasbih with 500 beads.

Until recently traditional tasbeeh with 33, 99, 100, 500, or 1000 beads were used. (Figure4) The differentiation between tasbeehs was based on the materials used to produce the beads and the shape or the frequency of beads. Plastics, different kind of trees such as olive tree, date tree, rosewood, or shelves or bones of animals, such as tortoise shell, or ivory, semiprecious stones such as cornelian, pearl, turquoise, or gem stones such as emerald, sapphire, and types of amber are some of the materials with which the beads of tasbeeh are crafted. Even rose water essence is added to the raw material of the beads to make scented tasbeeh. (Figure3)

Figure5. Rose-water scented tasbih of 99 beads.

In Turkish context tasbeeh is used for several reasons including giving social messages, expressing identity, showing fanaticism (Figure4) and the like. (Tonuk, 2011)

Figure4. Tasbih which shows fanaticism, the colour of the beads stands for a football club in Turkey

About 20 years ago, mechanical 'zikirmatik'⁵ started to be sold in the religious site where the field study is conducted. (Figure5).

Figure5. Mechanical zikirmatik.

In time, compasses were added to show the direction of Kaaba, where Muslims must head to when performing the salat. (Figure6)

Figure6. Mechanical zikirmatik, with a compass embedded to the back side to show the direction of Mecca.

Also some other different styles of these mechanical zikirmatiks are retailed (Figure7), but these relatively large tools were making a lot of noise when the mechanical button is pressed during dhikr, so the public usage of them was not preferable. Nevertheless, these mechanical products, which are manufactured in China by the order of retailers are still sold at religious sites in Turkey.

⁵ *zikir-matik* is the Turkish name given to digital counters. *zikir* is the Turkish word for allusion. *-matik* is a Turkish suffix used to suggest automation, quickness or practicality, for example ATMs, are called *Bankamatik* in Turkish, a usage similar to *banko-mat* or *vendo-mat*

Figure7. Mechanical zikirmatik.

When digital zikirmatiks were put on market about 5 years ago, they were welcomed with great enthusiasm by Muslims, as they were both smaller and made less noise. Different versions which were mostly the variations of small electronic goods, like tamagotchi toys (Figure8) or mp3 players (Figure9) were put to market.

Figure8. Digital zikirmatik in the shape of tamagotchi toys.

Figure9. Digital zikirmatik in the shape of mp3 player.

With the introduction of ring zikirmatiks, which are smaller and can be worn around the finger like a ring (Figure10), digital zikirmatiks started to be used in daily life of Muslims. These *ring zikirmatiks* were both smaller, barely visible from the outside, easier to carry along and made no sound. So they were integrated to the daily life easily. Keeping the numbers was easier with *zikirmatiks*, and usage was more practical.

Figure10. Ring zikirmatik.

Moreover, there are applications offered for mobile phones, which aid people in counting prayers. For example the iPhone application for dhikr, which is downloaded via iTunes, works by moving the thumb as if rolling the beads of a tasbeeh, prayers are counted with haptic interaction.

METHOD

The field study consists of 3 main parts. The first part is about the history of prayer beads that does not have a written historical account. Semi-structured interviews which lasted for hours that spread into different days are conducted with 3 of the shopkeepers out of about 10 shops at the religious site where the field study is conducted. The shopkeepers did not prefer voice recording, so I kept notes on my field diary not to disturb the trust based relationship that I have established during the inspirational study mentioned in the introductory chapter. I asked why prayer beads or digital counters are used and how these uses differed among customers. To inquire into the use and social context that shape these uses, I also asked who uses these objects and why traditional prayer beads or digital counters are preferred.

In the second part, semi-structured interviews are conducted with devoted Muslims, who obeyed the five pillars of Islam, and accepted Islam as a lifestyle and religious rules as a guide to inform their daily life. Eight male participants who attended the mosque regularly on a daily basis, and 13 female participants who were tarika members participating in the meetings in the tarika gathering house, a total of 21 participants who were of ages between 15 and 78 were interviewed. I asked about their daily activities and worshipping practices and why and how they pray to understand how Islam informed their life and the significance of their praying practice. Focusing on prayer beads and their recent

transformation into digital counters, questions on the meaning of objects, and their preferences between tasbih and zikirmatik, how they keep them why they choose that specific object are asked to understand the meaning and using of objects and how and why this usage changes between tasbih and zikirmatik. Moreover, whether they have used the object always the same, what they have used before zikirmatiks, and whether everybody practices the same with tasbih are asked to understand how practices and objects co-evolves how they position themselves in the society by using objects and how products influence their way of doing and negotiating. I kept on making notes during the interviews trying to keep the exact expressions participants used.

It might be necessary to note that this sample should not be thought of as a representative sample providing insight into the ideals, ways of doing, knowing and appropriating of whole Islamic groups.

In the third part, I made observations in the tarika gathering house and the mosque that I have visited for interviews. Besides, I observed the ritual worshipping practices that I was allowed to participate in, and made notes of my experiences. The observations were interpreted from my perspective and vision I formed via the literature survey I conducted, attempting to analyze the meaning of objects, consumption, specificity, materiality and the meaning of daily practices, ways of doing, and ways of orienting in the *habitus*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF THE FIELD STUDY

For the analysis of the interviews, the transcribed data in the form of field diary are interpreted through concept mapping, i.e. the transcribed text is grouped under headings, which refer to the concepts that rose in the theoretical framework on the use of objects.

DOING WITH TASBIH

Tasbih, in the sense of a tool used for the accomplishment of a practice, is used to count or accompany prayers. There are different kinds of

praying practices that require different tasbihs. For salat, devoted Muslims are sensitive to meet the requirement of reciting 3 prayers 33 times and pay attention to the precision of numbers, which they keep by using salat tasbih.

All of the participants, except for one, who is a 15 year-old student attending classes at a public school during the day, perform salat five times a day keeping up with the defined times. Except for one teacher of sociology at a public school, all of the participants were using tasbih to count the 33 times 3 prayers after each salat and they were using the tasbih with 99 beads, in which every 33 beads is divided by a smaller or differently shaped bead called 'durak' (stop), to mark the end of 33 times, so that the user knows s/he should go on with the other prayer from that bead on.

All participants expressed that in addition to salat they tried to dhikr in their spare time. One of the participants expresses it by saying:

"Does a Muslim ever have spare time?... a Muslim is supposed to worship and recite Allah continuously"

In these dhikr practices, as well as with salat, participants use tasbih to count or accompany their prayers.

Half of the participants (10 women out of 21 participants in total) who are members of tarika, pray by numbers and give importance to precision in number as prayers are assigned to them in numbers as *vird*⁶ by leaders of the tarika. Each member has a different vird, for example, as one of the participants state next to salat, her daily *vird* is as follows:

1000 times Salavat

1000 times *lailaheillallah*

1000 times *ya hafiz*

1000 times *ilahi şerif*

addition to these she says she has to complete 70000 times of another prayer per week.

Based on these examples it can be argued that *dhikr* and *salat* occupy most of their time. While waiting in a que, walking, travelling, they spend their time by performing dhikr, in an automatic, instinctive and routinized way, praying becomes the core activity of

⁶ vird are prayers assigned as homework

their life. And tasbih and zikirmatik that are used in the accomplishment of these prayer practices accompany devoted Muslims throughout the day.

For dhikr, they prefer using tasbih, which contains 100, 500 or 1000 beads without any stop, or zikirmatik. Mostly, those who have prayers as *virt* count their assignments by zikirmatik. They regard some prayers as of less importance and prefer counting these with zikirmatik. They also do their *virt* on their way to some place or while being busy with other things, hence they prefer digital versions as it is easier to keep the numbers. Those who use zikirmatik for prayers that are of less importance and could be recited without thinking much, prefer using tasbih at home and when they want to pray by 'feeling' the prayer. Also those who do not keep numbers, nevertheless use tasbih to accompany their prayers as a habitual behaviour, saying tasbih reminds them of praying and they pray more 'peacefully' and 'satisfied' while using tasbih.

Also each person has a different way of doing with tasbih. Some hold tasbih in their palm hanging over their index finger, and roll the beads one by one with their thumb towards themselves. Some hold tasbih between their thumb, middle and index fingers, pulling the beads towards themselves with index finger and thumb. Mostly, women hold tasbih in both of their hands with their palms slightly turned upwards and with their hands on their lap.

There are also expressions embedded in the use of tasbih. All male participants are concerned with the use of tasbih out of the purpose of praying, just to hold in hand as an accessory or as a symbol of authority in a group. If a man is swinging his 33 beaded tasbih in his hand, and showing off with it, it is a behaviour that is frowned upon, revealing one's low character. They favour tasbih to be held decently in one's hand, even in pocket without showing to anybody. As one of the participants says: *"It is not an accessory to swing in hand or so. Swinging a tasbih does not fit to a man, it is not appropriate, to sway a tasbih in hand to catch attention is not an appropriate social behaviour, kind of priggish I would say"*

In addition to different ways of doing with tasbih, there are also different ways in which tasbih is appropriated to serve for counting large amount of prayers.

Most of the devoted Muslims prefer using safety pin to mark the amount of their prayers. (Figure 11) For example, on a tasbih with 100 beads, after the first 100 repetition, first bead of the tasbih is marked by a safety pin, which marks the 100 prayers that have been accomplished. After the second hundred the safety pin is moved one bead forward. So the safety pin attached to the second bead states that two 100 prayers have been counted.

Figure 11. Tasbih marked with a safety pin.

Some others use the safety pin to mark where they are left in the round as well. One of the male participants explains his wife's usage as such: *"For example, during dhikr phone rings or door bell rings or she goes to check the oven so she marks where she was left and continues from where she was left when her task finishes."* So the use of object is appropriated to be able to perform the desired practice.

One of the women's usage was significantly different. She told that she had different zikirmatiks for each prayer and a tasbih for another prayer. She had one metal mechanical zikirmatik and two digital ring zikirmatiks of different colour to which she assigned different prayers, and was keeping their numbers separately. It was far easier for her this way, as the zikirmatiks show the amount on their screens. She carried all these zikirmatiks to everywhere in her bag. It is seen that the participant in this case gives different roles to the different zikirmatiks, and appropriates them to ease her practice.

One of the younger girls' usage was also different. She stated that she preferred using tasbih as she felt

she was not able to pray in harmony with zikirmatik. She said she used two tasbihs, one was to count up to hundred and the other was to count how many hundreds she had.

Mostly, participants have separate tasbihs for each salat and dhikr. The salat tasbih is usually rolled up with the prayer rug after the prayer was performed, or if the house has a separate praying room tasbih is placed next to prayer rug.

There are also some assumptions people have about tasbih, regarding gender difference. Most participants state that women use tasbih with colourful smaller beads, while men prefer usually black beaded tasbih with 33 beads. As one of the participants explains *“not a single man would use a green rosary, he uses dark colours.”*

Some participants mention the importance of the material that the bead is made of. Some choose their tasbih according to material. There are some materials such as pearl that they do not prefer. As they believe mother of pearl makes one sleepy, some participants state that they do not prefer such materials. One of the participants stated that she wanted a tasbih made of date palm, as Prophet Muhammad gave importance to date. Also the size of the beads and their frequency on the rope are important criteria. Some prefer tasbih which has no space between the beads, and some prefer having space about the size of a bead, so they use the tasbih more easily.

Based on the above examples it can be concluded that users, besides choosing the product in accordance with their ease of use, also appropriate them to achieve certain ends in which the product is not capable of doing itself, such as marking the beads with safety pin to be able to count to large numbers, or assigning different prayers to different zikirmatiks to specialize the product for their own purposes.

COEVOLUTION OF PRACTICES AND OBJECTS

As it is understood by the statements of the participants, digital counters entered into Muslims' lives with the introduction of *ring zikirmatiks*. Some participants stated that they also used mechanical counters and other forms of digital counters but

since these were making a disturbing sound when the small handle was pressed after each prayer, it was distracting both for the user and the environment. They were also too big, so it was not easy to hold in palm thus were easily noticed by others around.

As most participants, especially the women interviewed at the tarika gathering house, stated that with the help of digital counters, counting excess number of prayers became easier.

Apparently, zikirmatik has become appropriate for outdoor use. As one of the participants state: *“In daily life I use zikirmatik. Outside I mean, while travelling here and there, outside of the house. Tasbih is too demanding to use outside. Zikirmatik is easier, besides it's practical”*

Digital counters seem to bring about new usage areas. Especially with the introduction of ring zikirmatik, in addition to outdoor usage, women stated that they could use it while being busy with their household chores. They can go and have a look at the food in the oven and then come clean and tidy up the room, and do the laundry while still carrying the zikirmatik around. Some state they can even use it while knitting, and find it comfortable and easy to use. One of the informants stated she could dhikr even while driving: *“Thanks to Digital Counters I can dhikr while driving now!”*

As seen from the examples new usage areas are developed by the introduction of zikirmatiks. It can be argued that practicing belief have even become possible while doing profane practices such as travelling, knitting, and even driving.

SACREDNESS OF TASBIH

Most of the participants value tasbih as sacred, except for the one male and one female participants. Although the Imam⁷ states it is a wrong doing to attach sacredness to tasbih and there is actually no need for tasbih to be used in any circumstance, nevertheless he himself uses tasbih. He explains the reason as follows:

“It is not appropriate if all the community has tasbih but the Imam hasn't, not having a tasbih will

⁷ An Imam “is an Islamic leadership position, often the worship leader of a mosque and the Muslim community.” (accessed on Aug 25, 2011, from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Imam>)

be regarded as a lack in belief, so if I don't have a tasbih as the Imam, it will be regarded as a deficit"

Some people attach specific meanings to the materiality of tasbih, they state that they do not let other people touch or dhikr with their own tasbih. The excerpt from an interview below explains the reason behind:

"I get really irritated if somebody touches my tasbih. I get extremely annoyed. I don't let others touch my tasbih. This tasbih is shaped in your hands. Everybody reveals himself in the tasbih. The haram and sin are reflected on one's skin. The haram eaten, the sin committed by man is reflected on his skin. If a person who lives on haram touches my tasbih, the tasbih will go mad at me. Those who live on haram, stink... Likewise tasbih is shaped by man, it's the sweat and oil at hand" Feeling, touching and owning a tasbih, the feeling of bonding with Allah that the tasbih enables, the very materiality of the interaction with the most meritorious worshipping act is regarded as important.

Rather than the very materiality of tasbih as an object, it is regarded as sacred, as a symbol of Islam and a tool to reach Allah by most of the participants. Also another finding is that the sacredness of tasbih is closely related to the number of beads it has. Some say tasbih that has no holy number of beads could be used for other purposes such as an accessory. As one of the participants states: *"For example, the tasbih used for daily life should lack a bead. In this way it will not be a dhikr tasbih. Then it can be used as an accessory to swing or whatever."*

It can be argued that, the sacredness of tasbih results from the myths told in the Qur'an. As Yavuz (2006) argues that sacredness becomes attached to random objects because of the stories told in holy sources. So it can be argued that as one of the miracles showing Muhammad's prophecy was realized with praying beads, tasbih becomes sacred and comes to symbolize the belief in Allah, His power and almighty. The sacredness of tasbih also informs people's usages. Some participants stated that they did not prefer using tasbih that has Allah's and Muhammad's name inscribed on its beads. One of the participants told that she would not use such a tasbih as she had kids of her own and they might play with

it or drop it on the floor. Another participant stated that he did not prefer using such a tasbih outside, since he might go to toilet or so and it was not appropriate doing such things with such a sacred tasbih. Some other participants stated that if they saw a tasbih fallen on the ground they would take it and put it on a higher place.

IDENTITY DISCOURSE REFLECTED ON TASBIH

Rather than the ease of use, practicality, innovation in interaction and the sacredness, there is also a socio-cultural aspect of using prayer beads or digital counters, which can be argued as the primary reason for zikirmatik to be accepted by society.

All the participants regard tasbih as a symbol of Islam, Allah or their belief. They also assume that people from the secular groups in the society also regard tasbih as a symbol of Islam and the Islamist view, so seculars would associate tasbih with backwardist and religionist connotations. Therefore, most female participants state that they avoid using tasbih in public places, they rather use zikirmatik. As one of the younger girls in the *gathering house* says: *"I don't prefer using a tasbih outside, so that people don't assume me as hoca (religious leader). I mean if you carry a tasbih, they treat you as religionist"* She continues explaining *"Tasbihmatik [she names zikirmatik as tasbihmatik], in buses or so, makes one considerably at ease. Without anybody noticing, I do the virds"*. Some others who do not use zikirmatik, prefer hiding their tasbih in their bag, and dhikr with their hands in their bag, placing their bag on their lap.

One of the participants explains her distress as follows:

"In the past they would only stare, but now they even harass verbally. Saying 'those' are here again or 'they' are growing in number. They regard us as if we are the religionist extremists. Now that there is this kind of a polarisation in society, there is more pressure in comparison to the past. Therefore, I think it is needed to keep it quiet, and be patient for a while, I mean not to provoke 'them'... zikirmatik is more comfortable in this sense. Tasbih catches the attention of people around... They stare, harass verbally, look down at us, but with zikirmatik you can comfortably pray without being noticed. My husband uses zikirmatik as well. Among

people it doesn't catch attention, that is the most important."

As one of the shopkeepers in the religious site states this goes further than being condemned or harassed by the seculars. As he says: *"This country went through a 28 February coup⁸, there was a postmodern coup, ... military bothered the folk. They arrested those who were using tasbih and silver rings and such. So people tended towards those digital counters and stuff not to attract attention."*

It can be argued that based on the bipolarisation in Turkey between seculars and Islamists, Islamists negotiate their identity through the use of products. As it is exemplified in the above excerpt they neither give up their practices nor continue them the way they did, but by developing tactics they operate within the society, and position and disposition themselves through the use and appropriation of objects.

Moreover, zikirmatik is regarded as an innovation and something modern. For some participants zikirmatik is a sign of literacy and modernity, for others it means keeping up with the requirements of leading a modern life. Therefore, Muslims are keen on using these objects to express that they can also be modern and literate, and can embrace modern technology.

Also another participant provides a striking example. She stated that she had a lot of tasbih which she tried to match with her different outfits. She carries a black or brown at her bag, as these suit to most of her outfits, and she selects one other vivid colour which matches with the colour of her headscarf. So it can be argued that fashion and constructing oneself as fashionable within religious precepts is also a tactic in identity expression.

CONSPICUOUS WORSHIPPING DISGUISED IN INCONSPICUOUS OBJECT USE

Some participants state the reason for hiding their tasbih is due to religious constraints. *"I keep the zikirmatik in my pocket, and I pray conveniently, can*

one ever understand what I am doing? You can't pray outside, Allah says to hide the worshipping and the sin both, one should be modest. It would be a conspicuous act, to take out a huge tasbih and dhikr in public."

One of the male participants explains how he dhikr in buses, paying attention to not to show off with his praying. *"In buses, I hold my tasbih between my legs like this. If I sit in the front seat, nobody can see. Not to hide, but also not necessary to show. In mosques etc. I pray comfortably"*

Due to modesty which is regarded as religiously appropriate and respectable, they prefer hiding or disguising their tasbih or dhikr practice as other people might think they are showing off or being conspicuous of their prayer.

One of the participants has a significantly different opinion about this matter. She says she hides her prayer by keeping her tasbih in her bag to protect other people, especially seculars, from gossiping about her and thus causing them committing sin. She explains:

"In bus, I hold the tasbih in my bag like this. I would not prefer praying out in the open in a public that is unaware of religion. They'll say, look at her she is praying the tasbih, so they'll commit a sin just because of me ... That means she is condemning, she'll gossip, that is a sin. So to protect her, I disguise, not to cause her commit a sin because of me" And she continues suggesting a way of disguising a tasbih as a bracelet, (Figure12) explaining: *"if you say I cannot do without a tasbih, you can disguise it as a bracelet, with a matching outfit, so nobody would understand you are performing dhikr. I used to do so a lot in the past."*

Figure12. Way of disguising a tasbih like a bracelet, as one of the participants demonstrated

Muslims use and appropriate products for religious purposes, to live as proper Muslims and to live as they believe it should be lived like. For the specific case

⁸ 28 February coup (in other words the postmodern coup) is a process that is led by Turkish military against Islamic politics of coalition government in 1997.

of tasbeih and zikir matik which are the objects they use to aid in their most pervasive practice, they use these objects in various ways either to conduct a practice, express self identity or to organize daily life according to religious precepts.

CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed the thesis work which was inspired by an ethnographic field study. Material culture is emphasized as a way of analyzing object use within consumption and everyday dynamics. The method proposed focused on objects and revealed the importance of observing and being involved in the daily life of people to unfold the drives behind using a product.

In addition to an explanation on doing with objects and how objects are physically used and appropriated for the organization of life, social aspects of using a product are emphasized as well. How objects are utilized for identity expression and for constructing one's life and practices as it is believed as it should be are explained.

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